

DIGITAL PRESERVATION FOR ALL – THE DIGITAL PRESERVATION TOOLKIT FOR COMMUNITY ARCHIVES

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Abstract – The UK Arts and Humanities Research Council funded Our Heritage, Our Stories project researched the community archives landscape in the UK in order to document the challenges, issues and barriers facing community groups working to preserve both born digital or digitized content. It suggests the post custodial framework as a potential solution. The post custodial framework encourages established archive and digital preservation services and qualified professionals to provide support and guidance to community groups which will enable them to preserve, manage and provide access to their collections in a way that best suits them. The Digital Preservation Toolkit for Community Archives was designed as a resource to help facilitate this support while also allowing community groups to work on their digital collections in line with available resources and budget.

The creation of the toolkit was a collaborative effort between the Digital Preservation Coalition and a wide range of community archive representatives based across the UK. After a period of consultation, a toolkit matrix was produced comprising of a matrix framework with ten topics broken down over three levels. Working through the topic levels in order will lead to a functioning digital preservation workflow. Additional resources have also been created to provide additional support. Community groups are also actively encouraged to approach their local archive services for support and guidance to supplement the content of the toolkit. The toolkit was published on

World Digital Preservation Day 2024 and is now freely available online. Anecdotal feedback has highlighted some issues with the toolkit, including the UK centric focus and the DIY user format.

It is for this reason that further expansion and adaptation of the toolkit is planned to enable it to be a globally relevant resource which will be of use to a wide range of community groups across the world. A feedback process will be built into this process to make sure the toolkit remains relevant and useful to as many people as possible.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Collaboration between digital preservation practitioners and community led archives and organisations working voluntarily to preserve their digital content, has become a focal point of digital preservation discourse, particularly in the last five years. The Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) Global Bit List of Endangered Digital Species describes community archive content as ‘critically endangered’¹ and advises that immediate intervention is required in order to stop these important collections being lost or irreparably

¹See,

<https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/champion-digital-preservation/bit-list>

damaged. Community archives were again brought to the forefront of the conversation in 2022 at the iPRES conference, where keynote speaker, Tamar Evangelista Dougherty challenged those present to recognize community leaders as legitimate and necessary collaborators in digital preservation. That call was given fresh impetus in 2023 by Sherry Williams and Ricky Punzalan, both community group representatives, who further articulated the barriers and benefits of community engaged preservation and asked the sector for support with their work.

iPRES in 2024 broke new ground and further discussed the issue when, as part of the Arts and Humanities Research Council funded research project, 'Our Heritage, Our Stories' (OHOS), community group representatives were brought into the conversation. Their views were broadcast to the iPRES audience as part of a panel discussing the challenges faced by community groups, the issues preventing community collections from being correctly preserved for the long term, and possible solutions that digital practitioners could work with community groups to implement. The discussions at this panel and the outputs of the wider OHOS project highlighted that community groups were in desperate need of support and guidance from the digital preservation and archive sector in order to preserve their important collections. The Digital Preservation Toolkit was an attempt by the OHOS project to provide practical actionable support to these groups in a sustainable way that could be built on in the future.

The toolkit became one of the main outputs of the OHOS project and is now embedded as part of the main workstreams of the DPC. This paper will discuss the changing landscape of community archives over the last five years and why a toolkit like this was required. It will move on to describe the toolkit creation process and the continued focus on the views, needs and opinions of community groups themselves. Finally, this paper will look at what happens next, how the toolkit will be expanded, and how the DPC plan to continue this work. This paper emphasizes the importance of collaboration and

knowledge sharing to the survival of community archive collections and the stories they contain.

II. OUR HERITAGE, OUR STORIES AND THE POST CUSTODIAL MODEL

The Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) funded research project, 'Our Heritage, Our Stories', was one of five projects launched under the wider 'Towards a National Collection' (TaNC) programme.² 'Towards a National Collection' is supporting research that breaks down the barriers that exist between the UK's outstanding cultural heritage collections, with the aim of opening them up to new research opportunities and encouraging the public to explore them in new ways.³ Our Heritage, Our Stories was the only project of the five focused on community archives and the groups who care for them. The program launched in 2021 with The University of Glasgow, University of Manchester and the National Archives as main project partners supported by a wide range of stakeholders, including the Association of Learning and Technology (ALT), DPC and Wikidata. The project also included the views and opinions of over 25 community group representatives. OHOS was split into five focus areas known as labs. The AI, Archive, History, Linguistics, and Observatory labs worked together with a combined focus on documenting the complex community archive landscape of the UK and using technology to help support the community archives sector to not only preserve their records, but make them more discoverable and accessible. The history lab produced series of case studies which highlighted the work that five community archives based in Manchester were currently doing⁴, the linguistics lab researched the effects of language and cultural parlance on community collections, the archive lab carried out a research project which mapped the current status of the UK community archive landscape, including the challenges and barriers which were currently preventing their digital collections being preserved and accessed. The AI lab focused on the catalogue data produced by five specific groups and developed an open-source AI pipeline which ingested and reshaped the metadata

²For more information see, <https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk/>

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⁴The report can be found here, [https://ohos.ac.uk/wp-](https://ohos.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Manchester-Histories-Community-Archives-End-of-Project-Report-1.pdf)

[content/uploads/2024/11/Manchester-Histories-Community-Archives-End-of-Project-Report-1.pdf](https://ohos.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Manchester-Histories-Community-Archives-End-of-Project-Report-1.pdf)

into a standardised format.⁵ This data was then passed to the Observatory Lab, run by The UK National Archive, which absorbed and the data into a standardised catalogue format. A series of remixing tools were made available alongside the catalogue which allowed the groups to display their data in different ways and easily interrogate it. The project ran until January 2025 and produced a series of outputs, including case study reports, white papers, the observatory suite itself and the AI pipeline code.⁶

As a research program, the OHOS project aimed to show that it was possible to integrate community archive collections as part of a national collection in the UK with the correct support and resource in place. However, the research conducted by the archive lab highlighted that community archive digital collections are hugely fragile, the risk to the survival of community created digital records was high and without intervention, collections could be lost forever. Many community groups interviewed as part of the project indicated that they did not know how to preserve the born digital and digitised records in their care and were working under severe funding and resource restrictions. However, the vast majority of community groups indicated that they would like to maintain control of their collections and continue to work on them themselves with support and guidance as needed. The conclusions of this research (yet to be published at the time of writing) suggest a post-custodial approach could provide a solution to some of the challenges faced by community groups.⁷

The post custodial model was first mentioned by F Gerald Ham in his 1981 article, 'Archival Strategies for the Post Custodial Area'.⁸ The post custodial model puts archivists in an information stewardship role, where they provide the knowledge and support required for communities to, preserve, manage and provide access to their collections outside of a traditional repository. This theory has expanded in the digital age and provided a robust framework that allows established archive institutions to share knowledge and support, as resources allow, which

helps communities to manage their digital collections within their communities. In a bid to provide some of this support as part of the project, the DPC were invited to become a partner and create a digital preservation toolkit for community archives which would provide a practical pathway for community groups looking for help with their digital preservation work.

III. THE DIGITAL PRESERVATION TOOLKIT FOR COMMUNITY ARCHIVES – THE CREATION PROCESS

The Digital Preservation Toolkit for Community Archives (referred to hereafter as 'the toolkit') was an output from the OHOS project archive lab, created by the DPC. From the beginning of the project, the DPC were keen to produce a toolkit which would be of real value to the community. To ensure this was the case, the project began with a period of consultation. Community groups across the UK were invited to share their experiences, thoughts and opinions on managing digital content and to make suggestions on what knowledge and practical advice would help them overcome the challenges they were currently facing. Views could be shared via an online survey, by email or in a series of focus groups which were held online to maximise participation and ensure there would be no cost for those attending. This was a useful first step, as it allowed community groups to identify specific issues that the toolkit could help to resolve, but it also helped to confirm the levels of knowledge that the toolkit should cover. Without the consultation phase we would not have known that many survey respondents found the digital preservation resources already available online (including those previously produced by the DPC) overwhelming, full of jargon and hard to navigate.⁹ The consultation also made it clear that no two groups were the same, with some groups already having an established workflow that they wanted to build on, and other groups having no idea where or how to get started. The toolkit would need to not only cater for a range of experience levels but also for various stages of the digital preservation journey.

⁵GitHub repository available here, <https://github.com/OurHeritageOurStories>

⁶ <https://ohos.ac.uk/>

⁷ Footnote will be updated when reference to paper is made available.

⁸ The American Archivist
Vol. 44, No. 3 (Summer, 1981), pp. 207-216

⁹ Focus group recordings available on request.

Once this information was gathered and analysed, the drafting process began.

Based on the feedback gathered, it was essential that the toolkit was easy to understand and navigate, jargon free and contained practical advice that could be implemented with little to no budget or resources required. It was decided to present the toolkit in a matrix format, with three levels for each topic documented as part of the toolkit. Those at the very beginning of their journey could start with level one and work through all the included topics. They would then have the option to decide if they wanted to stay at level one or continue working through the additional content and tasks in levels two and three. The matrix format also allows those who are already working on digital preservation to pick a particular topic they would like more information on and start at the level that best suited them. In addition to the matrix, a suite of additional resources were included which provided more context to the digital preservation sector, what help, and support was available and a series of case studies from community groups already working to preserve their digital content.

IV. THE DIGITAL PRESERVATION TOOLKIT FOR COMMUNITY ARCHIVES – THE CONTENT

The final edition of the toolkit matrix included ten topics. During the first stages of drafting the matrix, it contained over 20 topics, all related in some way to digital preservation. In the end, it was decided that the matrix should serve as an introduction to the essential steps required to preserve digital content rather than attempt to cover every possible step associated with the task. Shortening the topic list also helped to avoid the content becoming overwhelming for those just starting out on their journey. A description of each topic is provided below.

First is **Choose / Create your content**, which describes how groups can decide what content belongs in their collections. Guidance is given on how to identify where your content will come from, how to absorb this content into your collections and how to select what content should be kept from what has already been accepted into your collections.

Next, **Organise Your content**. This topic focuses on how to name files, how to structure them in folders and the available options if groups would

rather use a system to manage this aspect of the process.

Topic three, **Who does what**, gives information on how to document what group member is responsible for each task and why it's so important to write this information down. This topic was included as community groups often rely on volunteers, who can leave with little notice, taking information like passwords or bank details with them. Knowing who is responsible for what task and how to reach them if required is an imperative step towards preserving digital content for community groups.

Understand Your Content is the next topic. It focuses on the content held within the group's digital collections. This topic describes how groups can easily document what content is held, where it is held and any other information the group feels is important to collect to the preservation of their collections. This topic makes the point that preservation of collections cannot begin unless you know what content you have and where it is. It also highlights that the information needed to preserve a collection will be in most cases specific to each group and helps the group identify what data will be of use to them based on the processes they have in place.

Topic five, **Keep Your Content** is about all things' storage. This includes where content is kept, how to review the current storage set up and how to decide what storage medium is right for the group. Storage is an important part of preserving digital content and it is essential that community groups understand their options, particularly in terms of ease of use and cost.

Control Your Content is next and is aimed at groups who are already using or thinking of using an external provider to store, preserve or provide access to digital content. Making sure you have options when you want to leave a system is not always thought about at the point of procurement or purchase. This topic includes a reminder to make sure groups always have easy access to their own collections and can leave a provider easily and with all their data and content if needed.

Make Copies is topic seven and is fairly self-explanatory. This topic explains why having more than one copy of all the digital content in the group's collections is so important and why every group should be making and keeping copies (at least one, but where possible multiple copies) of their collections. This topic is particularly important to the

many groups who store their content on websites and are unaware that they should have additional copies to ensure content preservation.

Topic eight, **Plan to Share** focuses on the areas to be aware of when planning to provide access to digital collections. Information rights, Copyright and General Data Protection Regulations are all covered and practical guidance is provided. This section of the toolkit is UK Specific due to the funding source for the toolkit. This issue will be discussed later in this paper under the what's next section.

Preserve Your Website is topic nine – OHOS project research and the project consultation phase work with community groups shows that a lot of community groups store and provide access to their collections online using a website. This level explains how to have the website preserved on behalf of the group using the internet archive. An easy do it yourself option is also provided in a later level.

Safeguard Your Content is the final topic and is about planning for the worst but expecting the best. No one wants to think about community groups, or any organisations working to preserve digital content closing down, but it is so important to have a plan in place for if the worst should happen. This topic helps with that in a practical way.

Each topic in the toolkit has been designed to contain a small amount of explanatory text and one practical piece of guidance that can be implemented by the toolkit user to help them move forward on their journey. For many topics, templates are included as are signposts to more information. As the toolkit was intended for those with no prior digital preservation knowledge, it was decided that the toolkit on its own did not contain enough context to get started, and so a suit of additional resources was added. These resources are described in more detail below.

What is Digital Preservation is the suggested starting point for those new to the topic. It describes what digital preservation is and most importantly, what it isn't. It also documents the difference between digitization and digital preservation, providing guidance on when each process should be used and why.

The consultation highlighted that many groups would like a roadmap to guide them through the starting steps of digital preservation. The **Just One Thing** document takes level one from all ten topics and pulls them together into one, easy to follow document. This can then be followed as a step-by-

step workflow which will result in a basic digital preservation process being implemented. The group can then decide if this process is adequate for their needs or if they would like to progress to the other matrix levels of each topic. The toolkit emphasizes the need for community groups to do what is right for the group and its resources. Some groups will be comfortable staying at level one and running a basic workflow, but others will have resource and budget to advance and implement additional tasks from later levels to further protect their content.

Part of the post custodial model is being able to approach established institutions for support and guidance. **You are Not Alone** is a resource that gives guidance on where to find institutions to approach, and how to get the information needed to preserve your collections. This resource explains the ways that established archive services can provide support and guidance with no expectations that groups collections will be deposited in the archive's repository. The next resource also provides support for those looking to engage with local or national archive services.

Explaining the Lifecycle is a resource that was designed to help facilitate conversations between qualified archivists and community groups. To reduce jargon used in the toolkit, the terms and phrases used throughout the record lifecycle are not used in the toolkit and the toolkit levels do not conform to the stages of the lifecycle. This document explains the links between the topics in the toolkit and the stages of the lifecycle, which will enable community group representatives to explain what stage in the process they are working at and ask for the support they need. Knowing how the lifecycle works will also help if community groups decide to progress further after using the toolkit and start working through resources created for the professional archive and digital preservation sectors.

Smaller additional resources include a series of **Case Studies**, which are also included in the toolkit to not only highlight the work that community groups across the UK are already doing, but to show what is possible and provide inspiration for community groups beginning to preserve their digital collections. A basic **Jargon Buster** is also included to help with terms, phrases and acronyms that are sector specific and may not have been encountered before. The final resource **What's Next?** provides a list of resources that may be helpful to community groups if they want to build on

the work that has been started by the toolkit. This resource also serves as a reminder that although working through the levels will provide groups with a functioning digital preservation workflow, the toolkit was not intended to cover every aspect of digital preservation and if the group feel confident in progressing their processes and policy then this is definitely an option open to them. The resources listed in this guide are grouped by topic for ease of use.

V. PUBLICATION AND IMPACT

The toolkit was launched on World Digital Preservation Day 2024 at an event held within the School of Advanced Study in London. Over forty community groups were represented in person and over sixty joined the event remotely. The day started with a presentation from Professor Lorna Hughes from the University of Glasgow about the OHOS project, included a toolkit launch and explanation presentation by Karyn Williamson, and six case studies from community archives based in London. Each case study focused on the work a particular group was doing around one of the topics covered in the toolkit. The day finished with a panel session discussing the potential of the post custodial model in bringing digital practitioners and community groups together and potential next steps that could be taken to improve collaboration between the two groups. It was acknowledged by both the panel and event attendees that professional institutions also face their own resource issues and budget challenges and, in some cases, may not be able to give the full level of support required from community groups. It was agreed that in these cases, communication is essential and collaboration across different networks and organisations may help to ease the burdens faced on all sides.

VI. WHAT'S NEXT

Initial feedback on the toolkit has been positive, although sporadic. At the time of writing the toolkit has been publicly available for less than six months and so no formal feedback process has yet been put in place. Despite this, two main issues have been collectively mentioned by those who have provided conversational feedback and plans are already in place to address these points.

Firstly, because the toolkit was funded by a UK research project grant, some of the information it

contains is UK focused. As mentioned previously, certain topics, such as 'plan to share' have been written based on British laws, policies and standards, which makes them of little use in a global context. In order to address this, a toolkit expansion project is currently underway. The toolkit is being reviewed to identify all the topics that need additional information added to make them applicable in a global context and this work will be carried out over the next twelve months. It will be impossible to include every Countries context, rules and laws, but we hope to make the toolkit as useful as possible in as many regions as possible, beginning with Australia, New Zealand and the USA.

Secondly, many community group representatives have commented that creating the toolkit and making it available simply isn't enough and training should also be provided to help community groups fully understand the content and implement it within the context of their own group. In response to this feedback, a second project is being undertaken to turn the toolkit into a free interactive learning resource. When signing up to complete the online course, participants will also be given the option of attending an in person workshop to discuss any challenges they faced when completing the training, ask for clarification on areas of the toolkit as needed and be given support to put a forward plan in place to document what steps their group should take next on their digital preservation journey. Individuals will also be able to attend the workshop first to find out more about the toolkit before completing the learning module. It is hoped that this approach will encourage groups to use the toolkit and feel able to ask for additional support as and when needed.

In addition to these projects, the toolkit content has been made available under a creative commons license so anyone can use it in their own learning resources or adapt it to suit their specific group context. A feedback process is also in the draft stages and the results of this will be used to further improve the toolkit content and format as required.

VII. HOW CAN YOU HELP

The main objective of producing the toolkit was to support community groups in a positive way to preserve and manage their digital collections. But this is only possible if community groups are aware that the toolkit exists. Continual promotion will be

essential to the success of the toolkit, and this is something that all digital preservation practitioners with links to community groups in their areas can help with.

In addition, we are always keen to hear any feedback on the toolkit, both from those who have used it and from those who have recommended it. It is important that the toolkit remains relevant, up to date and functional and your input can help with this. Contact details are available on the toolkit welcome page.¹⁰

VIII. CONCLUSION

As the last five years have shown, community groups and the digital collections they work to maintain are central to preserving global cultural memory. However, as the DPC Bit List categorisation of 'Critically Endangered' highlights, these collections are extremely fragile and at risk of permanent loss. The OHOS project highlighted that as a sector, community groups face many challenges and barriers to securely preserving their digital content. However, support and guidance from the established archive and digital preservation sector, particularly using the post custodial framework, can help community groups to overcome these barriers and put workflows and practices in place that will preserve and allow access to their collections long term.

The Digital Preservation Toolkit for Community Archives was developed to help community groups preserve and manage their digital collections in an easy to implement, standardized way. It is hoped that expansion plans currently underway will enable the resource to become globally significant and useful to a wide range of community groups all over the world. Adapting the toolkit into an online interactive learning resource will provide additional support to those at the beginning of their journey, and in person workshops will allow for specific support to be provided as needed. A regular review and feedback process will ensure the toolkit stays an up to date and relevant resource. Based on the post custodial model, the toolkit provides an avenue for established archive services and digital preservation practitioners to provide support in a way that allows

the needs and views of community groups themselves to be the focus point of all collaboration. Collaboration is the key to the success of the toolkit and both sectors will only benefit from continued connections and networking. Only by working together can these important collections be preserved and made accessed for many years to come.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Karyn Williamson holds an M.Litt in Archives and Records Management from the University of Dundee, a Post Grad Cert in Digital Information Management from University College Dublin and is a Registered Archivist. She is a Digital Preservation Analyst with the DPC and Campaign Manager for the Explore Your Archive Campaign.

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¹⁰The toolkit can be accessed at, <https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/implement-digipres/community-archives-dp-toolkit>

